

The digitalized medical services on NHS website: The changing role of 'patients'

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In recent years, a new digitalized system has been introduced by the National Health Service (NHS) in order to offer support and care to UK citizens. In particular, the Transformation Directorate at NHS England aims to drive the digital transformation of the NHS and social care. For instance, thanks to 'technology-enabled remoter monitoring' the NHS can deliver care to people in their homes. Starting from this assumption, this work is aimed at showing the significant role of corpus based tools when health services and care are offered to citizens. In particular, the immediate co-text of the nouns denoting the addressees of NHS policy is investigated in order to analyse the discursive strategies enacted by the NHS when people are informed about the new digitalized forms of healthcare communication. The study is based on a corpus based approach along with studies on transitivity processes, which will help to focus on the changing roles of the receivers of these new services. The outcomes confirm the existence of different lexical choice denoting the addressees of the NHS, thus revealing some changes due to the introduction of new digitalized tools of medical communication.

Keywords: Agency; Changing Roles; Digital Transformation; Digitalized Systems; Medical Communication; NHS

1. Introduction

The spread of the Covid-19 pandemic has had severe consequences for populations all around the world, mainly related to their health and rehabilitation practices (Cummings, 2021). Thus, the dissemination of medical knowledge and practices has become relevant in the post-Covid era, along with the improvement of digital health and services including telemedicine and teleconsultation, remote monitoring, connected devices, and digital health platforms.¹ Following these changes, some different roles acted by patients and doctors have been observed (Brown et al., 2006). For instance, during GP-patient consultation, counselling-based approaches have been introduced by teams of health professionals. These approaches emphasize the autonomy of the patients and shared responsibilities. Specifically, the use of open questions allows the patients to take part in conversations and decision making and the

professionals to show empathy towards the patients (Babaul-Hirji et al., 2010; Fairclough, 1995).

Starting from these theoretical premises, the present study tries to explore terminology denoting the people addressed by the NHS when the new digitalized forms of medical communication are delivered to them. The final aim is to focus on the changing role of patients, which may involve some changing practices in the interaction between the potential patients and the British institution.

Before focusing in detail on the procedure of the present study, some relevant information concerning the main services provided by the Transformation Directorate at NHS is necessary. The Transformation Directorate at NHS England is aimed at driving the digital transformation of the National Health Service (NHS) and social care. In particular, some key tools have been introduced over time in order to innovate medical communication. As can be read on the NHS website, the strategy for technology in health and care is to make the services digitalized, in order to facilitate service transformation.² Some strategies are mentioned, including "Data Saves Lives: Reshaping Health and Social Care with Data"—the Government's strategy which starts out a vision and clear actions to make better use of data to save human beings. Further tools included in the governmental actions consist of the introduction of the NHS Artificial Intelligence Laboratory (NHS AI Lab), which is aimed at addressing that challenge through the cooperation among government, health and care professionals, academics, and technology companies. Furthermore, an Information governance (IG) portal provides all the instructions concerning how to manage and share information cautiously.

Further tools are represented by digital playbooks, which have been introduced to support teams in redesigning care pathways and system support by showcasing tested technologies to solve real-world problems. Finally, people in need of special care can be supported from the comfort of their own home through technology-enabled remote monitoring. The Directorate also includes "The Innovation Collaborative for digital health a network." The network helps health and care professionals offering digitally enabled services to support people at home. As can be seen on the NHS website, while introducing these tools, the UK citizens are addressed to be informed about and involved in its activities and services. The corpus under scrutiny includes 35 documents listed in these subsections, which belong to both the institutional and legal field, namely (a) regulations, (b) delivery plans, (c) projects, (d) case studies, and (e) the introduction of the website's HTML pages. In the future, it would be interesting to focus on further case studies, blogs and forum in order to investigate the reaction of patients to these new digitalized medical services.

2. Background

Some previous studies from a discourse analysis perspective focused on some changes in health care communication. For instance, in academic writing, changing perspectives concerning proximity between physicians and readers have been explored (Donadio & Passariello, 2022). Furthermore, more attention towards patient empowerment and patient-centred medicine has been paid (Harvey & Adolphs, 2012). These changes are mirrored in shifts in contemporary discursive practices: for instance, the word 'patient' has been replaced by the more recent 'clients'. Shevell (2009) states that a passive role is implied in the word 'patient' while removing responsibility from the service user. Specifically, scholars from medicine, psychology, and social work state that the word 'patient' represents a paternalistic model of health care where this care is imposed upon people who are referred to as 'patients'. The term denotes identities, relationships, and power dynamics that convey the nature of social work, which also influences our perceptions and actions (McDonald, 2006; McLaughlin, 2009; Shevell, 2009). In contrast, the newer phrase 'service user' may have lost its function to describe the relationship between the professional and the person who uses services (McLaughlin, 2009). 'Client' has been often chosen with the intention of being more empowering and eliminating the 'patient' connotations (Shevell, 2009). It conveys a more active part in treatment and rehabilitation and involves responsibility for progress (Lloyd et al., 2008).

From a broader perspective in the linguistic field, language contributes significantly to the creation of fundamental practices that take place within a range of medical settings in healthcare and health communication, as it contributes to determine successful outcomes and patient satisfaction. It is also relevant to observe that healthcare communication is constantly changing, and through linguistic investigations it is possible to focus on the changes that are taking place and their direction (Harvey & Adolphs, 2012). Thus, in this work, an analysis of terminology denoting the people involved in institutional health communication upon being informed about the new digitalized tools and service offered by the Transformation Directorate at NHS will be provided. The final aim will be to shed light on the new role of the patient who is increasingly involved in the expertise traditionally associated to physicians and/or health professionals.

3. Method

In this section, more detailed information concerning the procedural steps will be illustrated. From a methodological perspective, a corpus-based approach (Baker, 2006; Flowerdew, 2012), by means of *AntConc* 3.5.9 (Anthony, 2017), helped to explore the immediate co-text of the addressees of NHS policy.

Theoretical studies on transitivity (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014) guided the data interpretation, as it is a notion that has been analysed from different perspectives (see Hopper & Thompson, 1980; Martínez Vázquez, 1998; Rice, 1987), although, perhaps, the most popular one is the Hallidayan perspective. According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), six process types can be observed—(a) material, (b) mental, (c) relational, (d) verbal, (e) behavioural, and (f) existential. The first three are generally considered to be the most frequent ones (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014).

Material processes (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014) mainly refer to abstract and concrete actions or events focussing on the idea of introducing some changes. These processes involve a main actor who takes part in material processes and is responsible for the change, referred to as the 'Actor'. There may be a further participant influenced by the transformations, who is denoted as a 'Goal'. Some subtypes of material processes may imply the changes of the Actor or Goal. Further participants are referred as the 'Recipient' (the person provided with goods), the 'Client' (the one a service is offered), the 'Scope/Range' (the one related to the domain over which the process occurs or the actual process itself, e.g., have a shower) or 'Attribute' (which is used to denote the resultant qualitative condition of either the Actor or the Goal, after the process is complete, e.g., they stripped her [Goal] clean [Attribute] of all her clothes).

Mental processes are related to our subjective experience. They involve (a) perception, (b) cognition, (c) emotion, and (d) desire. The main participants are represented by the 'Senser', or mindful being who understands, loves, hears, etc., and the 'Phenomenon', which may refer to any type of entity, conscious or not, understood, loved, heard, etc. The subcategories of mental processes include (a) mental cognitive, denoting thought and reflection (e.g., believe); (b) mental perceptive, referred to sensorial perception (e.g., see); (c) mental emotive, denoting feelings and emotions (e.g., abhor); and (d) mental desiderative, denoting volition (e.g., want).

The third and important process type to consider is relational processes, which, as opposed to sensing or doing, includes both inner and outer experiences, and represents the notions of being and becoming (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). In the study, attention will be mainly paid to the material processes, as they have been shown to be the most frequent ones in the whole corpus. Furthermore, the main focus of the study was to reflect upon the actual actions and plans offered by the institution to involve the patients into the new forms of medical communication.

The first step of the methodological procedure was to generate a wordlist in order to find the most frequent nouns denoting the addressees of the new digitalized forms of medical communication. Then, the immediate co-text of these words was investigated; in particular, concordance and collocate tools

helped focused on the transitivity patterns. As mentioned in the 'Introduction', the corpus under scrutiny includes 35 documents, which belong to both the institutional and legal field such as regulations, delivery plans, projects, case studies, and Introduction section of website's HTML pages and is made up of 105149 tokens. In Table 1, a list of the examined words along with their frequency in the corpus is provided:

The words in Table 1 were selected as they registered the highest number of hits in the frequency list. They denote the potential addressees of the information and services offered by the NHS. Future analysis could include pronouns in order to explore the strategies enacted by the Directorate to establish proximity with the users of the services (Hyland, 2010). Proximity is defined as a writer's control of the linguistic features which convey both authority as an expert

and a subjective position towards topics in progressing narratives. Thus, some future investigations could help to focus on the engagement of the institution while providing the citizens with new digitalized tools.

Table 1

Words and Their Frequencies

Words	Frequency
Patient	238
Patients	123
People	150
Individual	123
Individuals	79
Citizens	25
Citizen	12

Table 2

Collocates of the Word 'Patient'

Collocate	Rank	Freq (Scaled)	FreqLR	FreqL	FreqR	Range	Likelihood	Effect
confidential	1	160	10	9	1	4	47.764	4.790
information	2	6060	46	11	35	9	47.511	1.749
electronic	3	340	11	10	1	7	38.454	3.840
engagement	4	1020	16	0	16	8	34.888	2.796
charities	5	140	7	7	0	4	30.338	4.468
consent	6	400	10	4	6	3	30.133	3.468
will	7	11670	4	2	2	4	29.889	-2.720
explicit	8	220	8	7	1	3	29.738	4.009
shorter	9	10	3	1	2	1	24.376	7.053
representatives	10	90	5	1	4	2	22.703	4.620
records	11	1130	13	1	12	5	21.574	2.349
identifiable	12	190	6	1	5	4	20.689	3.805
outcomes	13	850	11	4	7	7	20.376	2.518
public	14	4170	25	9	16	8	17.808	1.408
record	15	1180	12	5	7	6	17.552	2.171
involvement	16	80	4	0	4	3	17.331	4.468
lacks	17	30	3	0	3	1	17.179	5.468
interests	18	90	4	1	3	2	16.411	4.298
safety	19	550	8	0	8	5	16.387	2.687

As can be observed from Table 1, the words 'patient', 'individual', and 'citizen' were found in the corpus in the singular and plural forms. Their function as premodifiers—mainly found in their singular form—was explored due to its high frequency. It is necessary to point out that a KWIC concordance of the word 'citizen' in Figure 1 instead of its collocates is provided due to the low frequency of this word in the whole corpus (only 12 concordance lines). In contrast, the choice of focusing on the collocates of the two other words (e.g., 'patient' in Table 2 and 'individual' in Table 3) rather than concordances was motivated by the need to make the data observation clearer because of the frequent occurrence number of these words:

Table 3
Collocates of the Word 'Individual'

Collocate	Rank	Freq(Scaled)	FreqLR	FreqL	FreqR	Range	Likelihood	Effect
an	1	3470	28	26	2	7	61.103	2.792
circumstances	2	140	8	0	8	1	47.109	5.616
care	3	14390	51	10	41	9	46.072	1.605
eligible	4	180	7	5	2	1	35.829	5.061
icss	5	610	9	1	8	1	29.289	3.663
or	6	4680	21	11	10	4	25.792	1.945
applicants	7	390	7	5	2	1	25.341	3.945
identity	8	70	4	2	2	1	23.542	5.616
suit	9	90	4	4	0	1	21.525	5.254
beyond	10	200	5	5	0	3	21.261	4.424
per	10	200	5	5	0	1	21.261	4.424
tailored	12	100	4	4	0	1	20.688	5.102
trusts	13	560	7	2	5	1	20.632	3.424
about	14	1860	11	8	3	3	18.181	2.344
purposes	15	470	6	4	2	3	17.912	3.454
lmns	16	60	3	2	1	1	16.848	5.424
because	17	180	4	0	4	1	16.099	4.254
identifiable	18	190	4	2	2	2	15.684	4.176

The results deriving from the observation of the Tables 2 and 3 and Figure 1 will be illustrated in the 'Results & Discussion' section. The second step of the investigation deals with the words in their plural forms (see Table 1). Particularly, the patterns where 'patients', 'individuals', 'people' and 'citizens' are found will be analysed in order to focus on the related transitivity processes and reflect on the changing roles of the actors taking part in British medical communication. The following KWIC patterns of the four words are provided in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5. Then, observations concerning their underlying transitivity processes underlying them will be outlined in the Results section.

Figure 1.
Selected Concordance Lines of 'Citizen'

The screenshot shows a concordance tool interface. On the left, there is a list of files under 'Target Corpus' including 'AI ETHICS.txt', 'AI REGULATION.txt', 'DATA STRATEGY ADVIS...', 'DELIVERY PLAN_digitis', 'DIGITAL PLAYBOOKS.txt', 'IMPLEMENTATION UPE', 'IMPROVING PUBLIC TRL', 'IMPROVING PUBLIC HE', 'INFORMATION GOVERI', 'INNOVATION COLLABC', 'INTRODUCTION.txt', 'NATIONAL PUBLIC ENC', 'NHS AI AWARD.txt', 'NHS AI CASE STUDIES', 'NHS AI CASE STUDY_M', 'NHS AI LAB.txt', 'NHS AI LAB_GET INVOI', 'NHS AI LAB-GET INVOI', 'NHS AWARD_CASE STI', 'NHS_AI IMAGING.txt', 'READ THE STRATEGY_f', 'TECHNOLOGY ENABLE', and 'THE CENTRE FOR IMPF'. The main area displays search results for 'citizen' with 12 hits. Each hit includes a file name, left context, the word 'citizen', and right context. The search query is 'citizen' and the context size is 10 tokens. The search is performed on 'Words'.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	READ THE ... ect health and care providers, improve outcomes and put the	citizen	at the heart of their own care. Our commitments
2	READ THE ... support a vibrant hub of genomics, imaging, pathology, and	citizen	generated data, where AI-enabled tools and technologies can
3	UNIFIED ... primary goals are delivery of: an improved user experience -	citizen	and professional an enhanced safety profile increased service effic
4	WHAT GOO... ealth and care outcomes by regularly engaging with partners,	citizen	and front line groups invest in regular board development
5	WHAT GOO... ICS would: develop a single, coherent ICS-wide strategy for	citizen	engagement and citizen-facing digital services that is led
6	WHAT GOO... nd coherent user experience ensure and monitor a consistent	citizen	offer by ICS organisations ensure a system-wide approach
7	WHAT GOO... a single, coherent strategy, in conjunction with your ICS, for	citizen	engagement and citizen-facing digital services that is led
8	WHAT GOO... ngle, coherent ICS-wide strategy for citizen engagement and	citizen-	facing digital services that is led by and has
9	WHAT GOO... egypt, in conjunction with your ICS, for citizen engagement and	citizen-	facing digital services that is led by and has
10	WHO DOES ... future state 1. EPR levelling-up and What Good Looks Like 2.	Citizen-	centred data/national digital channels 3. Federated data hubs 4. API
11	READ THE ... and senior manager, and perhaps most importantly as a UK	citizen,	I have both welcomed and valued the timely, focused
12	READ THE ... data is authoritative and reduce traceability of data for the	citizen.	Duplication of data also has an environmental impact. Where

Figure 2.
Selected Concordance Lines of 'Patients'

The screenshot shows a concordance tool interface. On the left, there is a list of files under 'Target Corpus' including 'AI ETHICS.txt', 'AI REGULATION.txt', 'DATA STRATEGY ADVIS...', 'DELIVERY PLAN_digitis', 'DIGITAL PLAYBOOKS.txt', 'IMPLEMENTATION UPE', 'IMPROVING PUBLIC TRL', 'IMPROVING PUBLIC HE', 'INFORMATION GOVERI', 'INNOVATION COLLABC', 'INTRODUCTION.txt', 'NATIONAL PUBLIC ENC', 'NHS AI AWARD.txt', 'NHS AI CASE STUDIES', 'NHS AI CASE STUDY_M', 'NHS AI LAB.txt', 'NHS AI LAB_GET INVOI', 'NHS AI LAB-GET INVOI', 'NHS AWARD_CASE STI', 'NHS_AI IMAGING.txt', 'READ THE STRATEGY_f', 'TECHNOLOGY ENABLE', and 'THE CENTRE FOR IMPF'. The main area displays search results for 'patients' with 12 hits. Each hit includes a file name, left context, the word 'patients', and right context. The search query is 'patients' and the context size is 10 tokens. The search is performed on 'Words'. The search results are sorted by relevance.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	AI ETHICS.txt the use of data for AI We want to involve	patients	and the public in deciding how and why ac
2	AI ETHICS.txt researchers and developers engaging with	patients	and the public about the risks and benefits
3	AI ETHICS.txt ope to demonstrate the value of involving	patients	and the public earlier in the development p
4	DIGITAL ... on, diagnostics and clinical teams. Provide	patients	with the information they need to effective
5	IMPLEMENT... lives. Improving experience and access for	patients	and people The Data Strategy set out a visi
6	IMPLEMENT... ease its functionality. For example, helping	patients	understand and act on information in their
7	IMPLEMENT... GP record, including test results, and allow	patients	to nominate a proxy who can access their n
8	IMPLEMENT... ccess their records on the App. One in four	patients	now have online access to their new health
9	IMPLEMENT... ber this year this should be provided to all	patients	unless they have individually opted-out or i
10	IMPLEMENT... timately improve the overall experience of	patients	and people. To support direct individual ca
11	IMPLEMENT... y 2030 and in turn improving the safety of	patients	and service users drawing on care in an inc
12	IMPROVING... rite views on the best ways to engage with	patients	and the wider public in an accessible way. 1

Figure 3.
Selected Concordance Lines of 'Individuals'

The screenshot shows a concordance tool interface with a search query for 'individuals'. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, Settings, Help), a 'Target Corpus' section with file names and token counts, and a main table of concordance lines. The table has four columns: File, Left Context, Hit, and Right Context. Below the table are search filters and a search button.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
8 READ THE ...	responsive services for children. Operating in a way that supports	individuals	to be active partners in their care also means
9 READ THE ...	that provide quick and easy access to information about the	individuals	in my care, even if they have been treated
10 READ THE ...	for information so I can spend more time with the	individuals	I am caring for all relevant information about individual
11 READ THE ...	the individuals I am caring for all relevant information about	individuals	in my care, including if they wish to share
12 READ THE ...	I feel empowered to access data for the benefit of	individuals	in my care and for the running of the
13 READ THE ...	nation about other professionals or unpaid carers involved in supporting	individuals	in my care so that I understand the whole
14 READ THE ...	be appropriate and accessible for the range of organisations and	individuals	relying on it. We need to change the culture
15 READ THE ...	access the most up to date information – this will ensure	individuals	only have to tell their story once, and that
16 READ THE ...	information they need, whenever and wherever they need it. Staff,	individuals	who draw on care and support, and their carers
17 READ THE ...	used successfully to provide more targeted care, such as for	individuals	with dementia living at home, preventing or delaying es
18 READ THE ...	safely and securely, respect privacy, and improve the experiences of	individuals	who draw on care and support. Technical and data
19 READ THE ...	health data sets to better understand and improve outcomes for	individuals	drawing on care Taking this further Improving access to

Search Query Words Case Regex Results Set All hits Context Size 10 token(s)

individuals Start Adv Search

Figure 4.
Selected Concordance Lines of 'People'

The screenshot shows a concordance tool interface with a search query for 'people'. The interface includes a menu bar (KWIC, Plot, File View, Cluster, N-Gram, Collocate, Word, Keyword, Wordcloud, ChatAI), a 'Target Corpus' section with file names and token counts, and a main table of concordance lines. The table has four columns: File, Left Context, Hit, and Right Context. Below the table are search filters and a search button.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
24 NHS AI CAS...	enabled us to identify and prioritise follow-up care for	people	who may have early-stage chronic kidney disease that
25 NHS AI CAS...	process is thorough but labour-intensive and with not enough	people	in the system, it leads to delays for women.
26 NHS AI ...	government and NHS partners. We are also engaging with the	people	developing and using AI, as well as members of
27 NHS AI ...	AI Lab are designed and run in collaboration with the	people	we hope will benefit from them. This page provides
28 NHS AI ...	information about some of the ways we are working with	people	to hear your views and shape our programmes together.
29 NHS AI ...	NHS AI Lab Virtual Hub is a community space for	people	to interact and share knowledge and ideas about AI (
30 NHS AI ...	you about the NCCID We have been engaging with the	people	using or affected by our imaging database to understand
31 NHS AI ...	including X-Rays, CT Scans, MRI, Mammograms, and Ultrasound. What	people	wanted to know Across the workshops run by the
32 NHS AI ...	know Across the workshops run by the NHS AI Lab,	people	wanted to understand how data about them is being
33 NHS AI ...	Our next steps From these workshops, it is clear that	people	are eager to understand the technical nuances around dat
34 NHS AI LAB...	NHS AI Lab Virtual Hub is a community space for	people	to interact and share knowledge and ideas about AI (
35 NHS ...	most likely to miss appointments. It customises communications to contact	people	in the most helpful way and links existing appointments

Search Query Words Case Regex Results Set All hits Context Size 10 token(s)

people Start Adv Search

Figure 5.
Selected Concordance Lines of 'Citizens'

The screenshot shows a concordance search interface for the word 'citizens'. The interface includes a 'Target Corpus' section with a list of files on the left and a main table of results. The table has four columns: 'File', 'Left Context', 'Hit', and 'Right Context'. The search query is 'citizens' and the context size is 10 tokens. The results show 17 concordance lines, each with a line number, a file name, a left context, the word 'citizens' in pink, and a right context.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
6	WHAT GOO... 5 collectively own and drive the digital transformation journey, placing	citizens	and frontline perspectives at the centre. All leaders promote
7	WHAT GOO... ey own and drive the digitally enabled transformation journey, placing	citizens	and frontline perspectives at the centre. Your organisation wo
8	WHAT GOO... and contribute to their health and care data ensure that	citizens	have access to care plans, test results, medications, history,
9	WHAT GOO... ICS Success measure 5 - Empower citizens What does good look like?	Citizens	are at the centre of service design and have
10	WHAT GOO... digital services that suit all literacy and digital inclusion needs.	Citizens	can access and contribute to their healthcare information, taki
11	WHAT GOO... ixes Success measure 5 - Empower citizens What does good look like?	Citizens	are at the centre of service design and have
12	WHAT GOO... digital services that suit all literacy and digital inclusion needs.	Citizens	can access and contribute to their healthcare information, taki
13	READ THE ... ensuring that they: provide benefits and improve outcomes for all	citizens	maintain respect for data privacy do not widen existing
14	WHAT GOO... I led Ensure smart foundations Safe practice Support people Empower	citizens	Improve care Healthy populations How we're supporting you
15	WHAT GOO... : digital support services across your ICS Success measure 5 - Empower	citizens	What does good look like? Citizens are at the
16	WHAT GOO... that is led by and has been co-designed with	citizens	make consistent, ICS-wide use of national tools and
17	WHAT GOO... to improve care by regularly enaaqing with frontline users and	citizens	invest in regular board development sessions to develop diqi

4. Results and discussion

The first observation is related to the most frequent lexis co-occurring with the words as premodifiers, as can be inferred from the collocates illustrated in Tables 2 ('patient') and 3 ('individual') and the concordances of 'citizen' in Figure 1. Specifically, 'patient' is mostly found in patterns such as 'improve patient care', 'share patient information', 'that is necessary for the purpose of processing confidential patient information in accordance', 'our aim is to provide information about how patient data is used', 'get more information about how patient data is used', 'we *need* to leverage maximum benefit from information to enhance patient care and improve services', as can be observed in the following instances:

- (1) We will support ICSs in making digital and technology choices, that drive value, help to reduce health inequalities, and *improve patient care*, ensuring this happens within a coherent framework (emphasis added)³
- (2) Progress so far
To support the COVID-19 pandemic response:
NHSX issued one page of simple information governance guidance to help staff access data with confidence, with the support of the Information Commissioner and the National Data Guardian

government used the Health Service (Control of Patient Information) Regulations 2002 to issue notices requiring public sector organisations to *share patient information* to support the COVID-19 response (emphasis added)⁴

- (3) The response to COVID-19 has been supported by the timely sharing of data under the COPI regulations 2002. Subject to specified safeguards (limitations, exclusions and approval processes), these regulations provide a legal basis for *the sharing of confidential patient information*, setting aside the common law duty of confidence for anything that is necessary for the purpose of *processing confidential patient information* in accordance with the regulations (emphasis added)⁵

This result emphasizes the institution's need to explore information about the patients and improve the knowledge and safety of the patient data. This is also confirmed by the high frequency of 'electronic', which mostly occurs in phrases like 'Electronic Patient Records':

- (4) Fully realising the benefits of digital technology *by increasing coverage of Electronic Patient Records* and Digital Social Care Records, so frontline health and care staff can spend less time on administrative tasks and more time delivering personalised care (emphasis added)⁶

'Electronic Patient Records' is a system whose aim is to have all patients with a centralized electronic health record. A slightly different co-text is found when 'individual' (Table 3) is examined. In particular, the word co-occurs with 'care', which is very frequent in some instances such as 'with all individual care information', 'to keep the public safe both for their individual care and to improve guidance and regulations', thus revealing the institutional interest towards the efficiency of treatments addressed to each individual. Finally, from the investigation of the word 'citizen' (Figure 1), it is possible to observe an institutional concern related to the involvement of the UK citizens into a deeper knowledge of the new digitalized services. The first step of the analysis also highlighted the significant frequency of the words 'patient', 'individual' and 'citizen' as premodifiers, more so than the nouns in their plural forms. This emphasizes a greater attention to the services offered rather than the people involved in this process. This result is confirmed by the occurrence of these words in phrases denoting the institutional need to improve care services and enrich information about the new digitalized forms of medical communication.

As far as the second step of this investigation is concerned, which is referred to the words in their plural forms and the transitivity processes underlying them, the first finding relates to the word 'patient'. As can be observed in Figure 2, the most relevant semantic field emerging from the context concerns the engagement and involvement with the institutions and the public. This data is

consistent with the most frequent words collocating with 'patients'—'and' (scaled frequency = 50400), 'for' (scaled frequency = 16380), 'with' (scaled frequency = 8460), 'public' (scaled frequency = 4170), 'service' (scaled frequency = 1440). 'Patients' are mentioned along with 'public' as Actors of the new medical forms of communication, as they are engaged with the institution, researchers and developers into the co-design of the processes involved, the knowledge of their risks and benefits, and the making-decision process. This also confirmed by the preposition 'with', which is mostly co-occurring in the pattern 'engaging with'. Nevertheless, 'patients' are also conceived as 'Recipients' and 'Clients' of the institutional actions, as confirmed by the high frequency of 'for' mainly in patterns such as 'the five principles to help NHS realise *benefits* for patients and the publics', 'Digital services enhance services for patients and ensure that they get the right care', 'enabling better care for patients hospitalized with a severe infection'. The two roles of 'Recipients' and 'Clients' seem to be relevant in the other words explored, namely 'individuals' (Figure 3) and 'people' (Figure 4). In particular, starting from the most frequent collocates of 'individuals' ('their', 'my', 'who', 'care'), 'people' ('care', 'at', 'with'), and concordance lines in Figures 3, and 4, it is possible to state that they are mostly addressed as receivers of doctors care but also as the reasons why professionals commit themselves to improving their digital literacy ('I feel empowered to access data for the benefit of individuals in my care', 'information about other professionals or unpaid carers involved in supporting individuals in my care so that I understand the whole', 'to identify and prioritise follow-up care for people who may have early-stage chronic kidney'). A more active role is implicit in 'citizens' (Figure 5), which mainly collocates with 'what', 'does', 'look', 'care'. These words refer to the 'What Good Looks Like (WGLL) programme, which is aimed at providing clear guidance for health and care leaders to digitise, connect and transform services safely and securely.⁷ 'Citizens' are addressed both as receivers of the institutional services ('drive the digital transformation journey, placing citizens and frontline perspectives at the centre') and as empowered individuals who are invited to take part in the new digitalized forms of medical communication ('Citizens can access and contribute to their healthcare information', 'that is led by and has been co-designed with citizens' make consistent').

5. Conclusion

The initial aim of this study was to explore the terminology denoting people addressed by the NHS about the new digitalized forms of medical communication in order to focus on the changing role of patients in the doctor/institution-patient interaction. The outcomes emerging for the first step of the investigation revealed more attention by the institution to the new services offered rather than the people involved in the process. This was

confirmed by the high frequency of the words examined in their adjectival function. This is probably due to the urgent institutional need to inform the people about the medical innovations rather than devote attention to instruct them on their use, although this data interpretation should be confirmed in further future investigations.

As regards the second step of the analysis concerning the investigation of the co-text of the nouns, a more active role was found, mainly in relation to the words 'patients' and 'citizens'. In particular, they are involved both as Actors and Recipients of the institutional actions. The active role of citizens could be motivated by their actual involvement in an institutional project aimed at transforming medical services. The active role of 'patients', instead, may be explained through their condition as subjects who are expected to already be part of the medical services as opposed to 'people' or 'individuals', who are mostly addressed as receivers of medical services and information.

In short, this study confirms the changing roles of the actors involved in medical communication. Specifically, 'patients' and 'citizens' are expected to interact with the new forms of medical services to obtain their own benefits. Nevertheless, in light of the higher institutional concentration on services rather than people involved in the process, in the future, more attention could be paid to the strategies enacted by the NHS to enable them to become more familiar with technological innovations.

Notes

1. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690548/EPRS_BRI\(2021690548_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690548/EPRS_BRI(2021690548_EN.pdf)
2. <https://transform.england.nhs.uk/digitise-connect-transform>
3. <https://transform.england.nhs.uk/key-tools-and-info/centre-improving-data-collaboration/centre-improving-data-collaboration-what-we-do>
4. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/data-saves-lives-reshaping-health-and-social-care-with-data>
5. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/data-saves-lives-reshaping-health-and-social-care-with-data>
6. <https://transform.england.nhs.uk/digitise-connect-transform/who-does-what>
7. <https://transform.england.nhs.uk/digitise-connect-transform/what-good-looks-like/what-good-looks-like-publication>

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